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Research article

A combination learning framework to uncover cyber attacks in IoT networks

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ABSTRACT

The Internet of Things (IoT) is rapidly expanding, connecting an increasing number of devices daily. Having diverse and extensive networking and resource-constrained devices creates vulnerabilities to various cyber-attacks. The IoT with the supervision of Software Defined Network (SDN) enhances the network performance through its flexibility and adaptability. Different methods have been employed for detecting security attacks; however, they are often computationally efficient and unsuitable for such resource-constrained environments. Consequently, there is a significant requirement to develop efficient security measures against a range of attacks. Recent advancements in deep learning (DL) models have paved the way for designing effective attack detection methods. In this study, we leverage Genetic Algorithm (GA) with a correlation coefficient as a fitness function for feature selection. Additionally, mutual information (MI) is applied for feature ranking to measure their dependency on the target variable. The selected optimal features were used to train a hybrid DNN model to uncover attacks in IoT networks. The hybrid DNN integrates Convolutional Neural Network, Bi-Gated Recurrent Units (Bi-GRU), and Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (Bi-LSTM) for training the input data. The performance of our proposed model is evaluated against several other baseline DL models, and an ablation study is provided. Three key datasets InSDN, UNSW-NB15, and CICIoT 2023 datasets, containing various types of attacks, were used to assess the performance of the model. The proposed model demonstrates an impressive accuracy and detection time over the existing model with lower resource consumption.

1. Introduction

The traditional networking infrastructure comprises several networking equipment, including switches, routers, and intermediary devices, in which application-specific integrated circuits are put to carry out specialized functions [1,2]. To accomplish the specified duties, the devices are pre-programmed with various sophisticated rules (i.e., protocols), which cannot be changed in real-time [3]. Furthermore, the devices' resource limitations prevent them from being pre-programmed with several rules to deliver the best network services. As a result, existing network technologies are unable to quickly implement the required regulations to satisfy the application-specific needs of the Internet of Things (IoT). The IoT has evolved as a paradigm-shifting idea that is revolutionizing how we interact with technology and our surroundings. It stands for a huge network of linked devices, sensors, and systems that can gather, share, and process data in real-time. Theoretically, an IoT system is totally secure if it implements all necessary security standards, but in practice, things are more challenging. The IoT is vulnerable to different cyberattacks such as Distributed Denial

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Fig. 1. An SDN-assisted IoT architecture.

of Service (DDoS), probe, Ransomware, botnet assault; just like any other computer network system. Such attacks are posing significant risks to individuals, organizations, and critical infrastructure. Due to the weak security measures, IoT devices can be easily compromised and added to botnets. Attackers can then launch massive DDoS attacks by coordinating the compromised devices to overwhelm targeted systems or networks with a flood of traffic, rendering them unavailable [4,5]. As the network expands, it becomes crucial to uphold such qualities as scalability and reliability. Software-defined networks (SDN) offer a solution by enhancing the flexibility and adaptability of networks. With the ability to swiftly adapt to evolving business requirements, SDN aims to augment network control. The SDN-assisted IoT architecture often referred to as SDIoT, assists in resource management while ensuring optimal network performance [5,6].

In recent times, numerous cyber-attacks have targeted IoT networks. For instance, in October 2016, a DDoS attack utilizing the Mirai Botnet impacted Dyn Server—a company responsible for managing a significant portion of the Internet’s DNS infrastructure in America. This attack affected major websites like Amazon, Spotify, PayPal, and Twitter in the United States and Europe. Cybersecurity researchers at Trend Micro discovered that this attack compromised 122,069 IP cameras worldwide [6]. These recent cyber attacks on IoT networks have resulted in considerable device damage, serving as the driving force behind our study.

To protect from sophisticated cyberattacks, it is a top priority to deploy intelligent solutions in IoT-based applications quickly. Therefore, the SDN-like framework needs to be acknowledged for various attack problems. Fig. 1 discussed a Software Defined-IoT architecture where IoT-enabled devices generate a large volume of data from the end users. Further, a communication network is formed by all edge devices (base stations) and they act as the forwarding plane of the SDN network. The controller manages each base station and is responsible for maintaining the security of the entire communication network.

Due to the recent progress in machine learning techniques, there has been a notable shift in various studies, moving away from rule-based detection methods such as ingress filtering to ML-based detection strategies [7]. Specifically, deep learning approaches have emerged as a compelling choice, particularly well-suited for handling intricate input data and recognizing complex patterns.

IoT systems often have limited computational resources [8]. To address this, reducing the number of features in a resource-constrained environment is essential for creating a lightweight attack detection model. This reduction helps alleviate the computational burden on devices, leading to improved performance in anomaly detection tasks. Moreover, effectively detecting anomalies from the massive amounts of high-dimensional data in IoT remains a challenging task. Artificial Intelligence (AI), particularly deep learning and machine learning has been widely adopted for anomaly detection in numerous applications. Such factors motivate us to design a DDoS detection system in an SDIoT environment. The major contributions of the paper are listed below.

- This work employs a robust feature selection technique followed by a hybrid Deep Neural Network (DNN) architecture to uncover cyber attack traffic. The DNN architecture integrates Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) with cost-effective convolutional layers and includes Bi-GRU and Bi-LSTM layers. These components are designed to enhance the model’s ability to detect attacks accurately.
- The study employs a Genetic Algorithm (GA) with correlation metric as fitness functions to determine the most relevant features from network traffic data. To improve the selection process, mutual information is used to rank the features, measuring their dependency on the target variable.

Table 1
Abbreviations list.

Abbreviations list	Description	Abbreviations list	Description
SDIoT	Software Defined IoT	BN	Batch Normalization
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance	XGBoost	Extreme Gradient Boosting
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory	GRU	Gated Recurrent Unit
PSO	Particle Swarm Optimization	SA	Simulated Annealing
OF	OpenFlow	GAFS	Genetic Algorithm based Feature Selection
FS	Feature Selection	ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit
PCA	Principal Component Analysis	SD	Standard Deviation
SVM	Support Vector Machine	MCC	Matthews Correlation Coefficient
DT	Decision Tree	RF	Random Forest
ROC	Receiver Operating Curve	AUC	Area Under Curve
MI	Mutual Information	MFLOPs	Mega Floating-Point Operators

Organization. The rest part of the paper is segmented as follows. Related work on feature optimization techniques for anomaly detection is discussed in Section 2. The proposed methodology is explained in Section 3. Section 4 provides the experimental results, which are summarized in Section 5. Finally, the conclusion and future works are reviewed in Section 6. The list of abbreviations and their meanings are given in Table 1.

2. Background

2.1. SDN-assisted IoT

SDN is an architectural framework for network management and control that divides the control plane from the data plane of a network [6,9]. Traditionally, network hardware like switches and routers perform both data forwarding and control. These tasks are separated into an SDN, enabling network programming and central management. Using a standardized protocol, such as OpenFlow (OF), the controller instructs the network devices on how to manage traffic flows [10]. The control plane makes high-level choices on routing, traffic prioritization, security guidelines, and other network behaviors.

SDIoT combines IoT and SDN to connect objects over the Internet by decoupling the control plane and the data plane [11]. It uses SDN to provide a centralized control plane that can manage and secure IoT devices. It can provide a more flexible and scalable network architecture for IoT devices. It provides better security for IoT devices by allowing for more granular control over network traffic and access. SDN provides better visibility into IoT devices and their behavior, making it easier to detect and respond to various security threats [6].

2.2. Feature selection and genetic algorithm

Feature selection (FS) is the process of selecting a subset of the original characteristics to reduce model complexity and reduce generalization error caused by noise provided by irrelevant features [12]. The values of the features present in the benchmark dataset might be continuous or ordinal. As a result, the deployment of a dimension reduction mechanism is not sufficient to conclude. Therefore, a metaheuristic-based feature selection technique has been deployed. The Genetic Algorithm (GA) is a heuristic global search mechanism that is inspired by biological evolution [13]. It is used to address both limited and unconstrained optimization problems. The GA maintains a population of chromosomes associated with fitness values. It can be used for FS by searching the optimal subset of features that maximizes a given performance metric, such as classification accuracy or regression error.

2.3. Deep neural network

DNN gained significant attention and popularity due to its ability to automatically learn patterns and representations from large and complex datasets, making it well-suited for various applications. DNN comes in various architectures, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), transformers, etc. Each model is designed for specific tasks and problem domains.

The long short-term memory (LSTM) is a type of RNN that was developed to solve the limitations of conventional recurrent neural network architecture. Through the utilization of dedicated memory cells and gating mechanisms, information is selectively retained or discarded over time by the long short-term memory (LSTM) model. The input gate (IG) controls the flow of information into the current cell state through the point-wise multiplication of σ and \tanh functions. This makes it particularly well-suited for applications involving sequential data. An LSTM cell can be modeled by using the following equations. The forget gate (FG) is denoted as,

$$f_t = \text{sigma}(W_f \cdot x_t + U_f \cdot h_{t-1} + b_f) \quad (1)$$

The input and output gate values are represented in Eqs. (2) and (3).

$$i_t = \text{sigma}(W_i \cdot x_t + U_i \cdot h_{t-1} + b_i) \quad (2)$$

$$o_t = \text{sigma}(W_o \cdot x_t + U_o \cdot h_{t-1} + b_o) \quad (3)$$

$$c_t = \text{tanh}(W_c \cdot x_t + U_c \cdot h_{t-1} + b_c) \quad (4)$$

$$c_t = f_t \cdot c_{t-1} + i_t \cdot c'_t \quad (5)$$

$$h_t = o_t \cdot \text{tanh}(c_t) \quad (6)$$

where, f_t represents the FG, i_t is the IG, o_t is the OG, c_t is the cell state and h_t is the hidden state. The $W_i, W_o, W_c, U_f, U_i, U_o, U_c$ represent the weights and b_f, b_i are the bias.

On the other hand, bi-LSTM (Bidirectional LSTM) analyses input sequences both forward and backward. The forward LSTM processes the historical data of the input sequence, while the reverse LSTM captures the future data information within the sequence. Subsequently, the outputs from both hidden layers are merged. At any given time t , the hidden state h_t in Bi-LSTM contains information from both-way passes.

$$h_t = \text{forward}(h_t) \oplus \text{backward}(h_t) \quad (7)$$

where \oplus represents component-wise summation, combining both forward and backward components.

On the other hand, GRU (Gated Recurrent Unit) is simpler and more efficient than LSTM. The reset gate controls how much of the previous hidden state is kept, and the update gate controls how much of the new input is added to the hidden state. The Eq. (8) shows how the reset gate is evaluated.

$$g_t = \text{sigma}(R_r \cdot h_{t-1} + Q_r \cdot x_t + o_r) \quad (8)$$

where g_t is the reset gate, R_r, Q_r , and o_r are the recurrent weight matrix, input weight matrix, and bias, respectively. x_t is the input at time t and h_{t-1} is the hidden state at $t-1$.

3. Related work

This section presents existing research on feature selection techniques, used datasets, and ML/DL classification algorithms used for attack detection in network Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs), SDN, and IoT Networks. The comparison of various methods with the proposed model is summarized in Table 2.

3.1. Machine learning-based approaches

Researchers have invested their interest in designing effective DDoS detection using various ML algorithms [14,15]. Classifiers like Nave Bayes (NB), support vector machine (SVM), k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), and random forest (RF) presented impressive detection results for detecting malicious flows. In [16], a bio-inspired bat algorithm for identifying HTTP flood attacks was introduced. In [14], authors demonstrated a detection mechanism based on the Pearson correlation method. The testing phase is developed to detect any abnormal traffic by measuring the difference between normal and malicious traffic using various ML approaches. Türkoğlu et al. suggested minimum redundancy maximum relevance (MRMR) technique used for feature selection and Bayesian-based decision tree classifier has been utilized for attack traffic detection [17]. Aguru et al. [18] implemented a lightweight DDoS detection mechanism for IoT networks using entropy and expectation of packet size. The mechanism employs feature engineering on network traffic characteristics to classify incoming IoT traffic. In another work, Gaur et al. [19] presented a hybrid model that combined ML and FS algorithms to improve the model performance on the CICDDoS19 dataset. For the early attack detection on the IoT system, chi-squared tests and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were employed, and KNN, DT, and XGBoost were used as the detectors. In [20], the authors proposed the CorrAUC framework, which studied wrapper techniques to filter the features and further explored various ML techniques for the detection of anomaly traffic. Likewise, Muhammad Ismail et al. [21] utilized ML classifiers with model optimization techniques for DDoS attack classification. The XGBoost technique addressed kernel hyperparameter tuning to enhance performance. The suggested framework was validated through the KDD and UNWS-NB15 datasets. Malik et al. [22] suggested a two-stage detection system designed for the IoT-CIDDS dataset. The first stage is for FS using random forest, and the second is for classification using SVM and DT techniques.

3.2. Deep learning-based approaches

To make the system more robust and accurate, researchers have implemented DL for predicting meaningful patterns from the network traffic. The design and implementation of an RNN-IDS detection system based on recurrent neural networks were suggested

Table 2
Succinct analysis of relevant prior works.

Reference	year	Feature selection	Classification method	Dataset	Environment	Limitations
FS with Machine Learning-Based Approaches						
Shafiq et al. [20]	2020	Correlation and AAUC	DT, SVM, NB, RF	BoT-IoT	IoT network	Focused on FS but not discussed implication of IoT network
Hafeez et al. [37]	2020	N/A	Fuzzy C means clustering	YTY2018, self-generated	IoT network	Training/testing time and IoT traffic were not considered.
Kasongo et al. [38]	2021	GA	ET, NB, DT, LR	UNSWNB15	IIoT	Utilized only dependent features, and CPU and memory usage are not discussed.
Mohmand et al. [21]	2022	N/A	UNSWNB-15	XGBoost, Random Forest (RF)	Network IDS	Few features are dependent and no IoT dataset was considered.
Gyamfi et al. [14]	2022	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	Incremental support vector data description and EML	UNSWNB-15, testbed generated	Industrial IoT	considered only 15 features in both datasets, no SDN traced traffic considered.
Malik et al. [22]	2023	RF	SVM, DT, LR, RF, MLP	IoT-CIDDoS	IoT network	Study lacks discussion on specific attack types.
FS with Deep Learning-Based Approaches						
Mustafa et al. [39]	2018	ICA	Multi hidden Markov Model	UNSW-NB15, CPS	Industry 4.0	Not considered heterogeneous traffic and did not compare with DL models.
Roopak et al. [34]	2020	NSGA-II	ELM	CICIDS2017	IoT Network	compared with old IoT dataset
Su et al. [40]	2020	Attention mechanism	Bi-LSTM with attention	NSL-KDD	Network IDS	No comparison with other RNN variants
Andresini et al. [41]	2020	N/A	Autoencoders	KDDCup99, UNSW-NB 2015, CICIDS2017	Network IDS	lacks details information on the structure and characteristics of the attacks
Laghrissi et al. [28]	2021	PCA and MI	LSTM	NSL-KDD	Network IDS	only tested one type of LSTM model
Otoum et al. [42]	2022	spider monkey optimization algorithm	stacked-deep polynomial network	NSL-KDD	IoT	convergence analysis and train/test time were not investigated.
Cvitić et al. [43]	2022	N/A	Logistic model tree	testbed dataset	IoT	accuracy could be enhanced
Khanday et al. [44]	2023	tree-based model	LSTM	BOT-IoT and YON-IoT	IoT	over fitting to noisy data
Chander et al. [30]	2023	deer hunting optimization algorithm	CRNN	UCI SECOM	Industrial IoT	convergence analysis was not examined.
Priyadarshini et al. [27]	2023	N/A	Attention with Bi-LSTM-CNN	DDoS-SDN dataset	SDN	RNN model like GRU and Bi-GRU were not examined.
Sahu et al. [45]	2022	N/A	LSTM and FCN	KDD, Kyoto, NITRODS	Network IDS	Computation of the models were not discussed.
Proposed Approach	2023	GA	LSTM, Bi-LSTM, Bi-GRU	InSDN, UNSW-NB-15	SDIoT	energy usage of the model has not discussed.

by Yin et al. [23]. Fang et al. [24] suggested a malicious JavaScript code detection model based on LSTM. Shabtai et al. [25] developed a flexible and adaptive time series anomaly detection technique based on the LSTM encoder–decoder model. Authors have injected malicious data into automatic dependent surveillance-broadcast (ADS-B) messages. A DL model, specifically a neural network made up of numerous stacked fully connected layers, was proposed by Toupas et al. [26]. Priyadarshini et al. proposed an adaptive anomaly detection framework model using attention-based Bi-LSTM with CNN [27]. The model is evaluated using standard DDoS-SDN datasets. A three-layer LSTM model was presented by Laghrissi et al. [28]. Both PCA and MI were explored for both binary and multi-class feature classification. In [29], authors suggested a GRU model instead of normal LSTM networks for possible reduced training times. In [30], the authors introduce a novel feature selection technique by devising a deer hunting optimization algorithm. This method identifies a valuable subset of features. Moreover, they employ a cascaded recurrent neural network (CRNN) system to detect and classify anomalies.

3.3. Meta-heuristic-based feature selection

Tahir et al. [31] suggest an FS method based on GA with chaotic maps. The model was tested on affective computing and the healthcare environment. Chaotic maps are used for the initial population of the GA, followed by the reproduction processes to generate the best feature set. An improved binary Whale optimization algorithm for FS was proposed by Xu et al. [32]. The authors evaluate the model on the KDD dataset. It is evident that such techniques converge slowly and may fall into the local optima during the updating mechanism, which may affect the classification. Fan et al. [33] evaluate a steering-matrix-based multi-objective evolutionary algorithm (SM-MOEA), which is suitable for high-dimensional feature selection (FS). Monika et al. [34] proposes a multi-objective optimization-based feature selection method for detecting DDoS attacks in IoT networks. They have implemented the non-dominated sorting algorithm with its adapted jumping gene operator to solve the optimization problem. A GA-based FS with a novel fitness function was proposed by Halim et al. [35]. Maza, Sofiane et al. [36] proposed MOEDAFS a multi-objective feature selection algorithm for IDS. The algorithm uses Estimation of Distribution Algorithms (EDA) and Mutual Information to select significant features and improve classification performance.

3.4. Research gap

From the related work, we observed that a plethora of work has been carried out to address the problems of network IDS in SDN and IoT scenarios. However, the state-of-the-art approaches have been studied in isolation rather than leveraging features of classical, statistical, and deep learning approaches. Consequently, we decided to explore developing a hybrid DL model by combining approaches within a resource-constrained environment, precisely for IoT networks. It is worth noting that DL-based solutions often

demand substantial computational resources for learning and performing detection tasks [46]. Hence, efficient feature selection combined with model-based methods on large datasets can yield promising results. Prior research often relies on automatic feature learning and feature extraction. Notably, the concept of selecting the most relevant features before applying DL models has not been extensively explored in IoT dataset in SDN settings. Most often, traditional datasets have been considered and given less importance to the SDN and IoT testbed datasets.

Addressing these gaps is crucial for advancing the state-of-the-art in attack detection for IoT networks and enhancing the security of IoT deployments in real-world settings.

3.5. Problem statement

Accurately classifying normal and malicious traffic in a large-scale IoT environment is challenging. At the same time, designing a lightweight defense framework for potential cyberattacks in IoT is pivotal.

SDN-assisted IoT defense system enhances security by allowing full control over underlying network devices. Such defense system needs to handle a wide range of network traffic types. The traffic that the SDN controller needs to monitor and analyze can include normal traffic (Device-to-Device, Device-to-Gateway Communication traffic), various malicious traffic (DDoS, Probe, Mirai, U2R), and protocol-specific traffic (HTTP, TCP) among others. Selecting key features from these data is important to make the attack detector more sophisticated and effective for the identification of malicious attacks.

When the class labels are available, the feature selection is somewhat more precise as the impact of each feature depends on predicting the class label. However, feature selection can be carried out unsupervised in the context of not having class labels. The utilization of unsupervised feature selection techniques introduces complexity due to the extensive evaluation of multiple combinations during the process of optimal feature subset selection. The challenge here is to devise an enhanced unsupervised feature selection technique, for which we consider employing the evolutionary algorithm. On the other hand, existing deep learning models with complex architectures demand more computational time [1,8]. Therefore, the objective is to select the optimal number of features using an evolutionary feature selection technique from different large network datasets to build a computationally-effective hybrid DL model for the SDN-assisted IoT networks.

4. Proposed framework

The SDN controller handles all the communication between applications and the data plane. The OF is responsible for allowing the controller to communicate with network devices. The application layer allows the controller to communicate with different modules such as load balancer, IDS, network monitoring, and flow management. An efficient and low-complexity IDS is required to design as the controller is responsible for many tasks, especially in an IoT scenario. In this article, we propose a GA-based FS and a hybrid DNN technique for cyber attack detection in such an environment. The workflow of the proposed framework is shown in Fig. 2. At first, the CICFlowmeter captures the network traffic on the core network and extracts all traffic features. Further data pre-processing is needed to get the quality data. The proposed framework runs over the controller and exploits the FS technique to extract the best optimal feature subset. The important features are further fed into the DL model to detect the traffic as normal or attack traffic.

4.1. Evolutionary feature selection

Based on their selection strategies, FS methods can be classified into three distinct categories: wrapper, filter, and embedded methods. The issue with the wrapper technique is that the search space of a n feature dataset increases to 2^n , which is challenging for a larger-dimension dataset. On the other hand, the filter methods are not dependent on the learning algorithms. Although these methods are better than wrapper techniques, the ranking criteria of these methods primarily influence the selection process. Embedding methods may lead to information loss and are often computationally expensive. Wrapper methods like forward selection and backward elimination can lead to suboptimal selections due to their deterministic nature. In these methods, eliminated features are not considered again for inclusion. Hence, these search strategies are likely to lead to local optimal selections. Heuristic search methods, such as genetic algorithms, simulated annealing (SA), and particle swarm optimization (PSO), can theoretically find optimal solutions through well-designed algorithms [47]. GA is particularly effective in feature selection, often outperforming local search methods.

Filter-based FS algorithms typically select top-ranked features based on their evaluation, which is straightforward but can lead to local optima. In contrast, GA explores solution spaces efficiently and maintains low computational loads. GA has been used as a search strategy for FS in much of the literature. However, the vast majority follow GA as the wrapper approach. To leverage GA's global search capability and filter-based evaluations, we propose an FS algorithm that combines GA searching with a mutual information-based filter criterion. The proposed method contains two steps. In the filter phase, we arrange features based on their MI with category labels in descending order. It enables us to prioritize features for the genetic algorithm's initial population based on their MI values. In the wrapper phase, we employ a GA as the search strategy.

GA works on the different genetic parameters such as initial population, fitness function, selection strategy, cross-over, mutation, and next-generation production, which are discussed below.

Fig. 2. Workflow of the proposed cyber attack detection model in SDN-assisted IoT networks.

- **Chromosome structure:** Chromosomes are built by randomly combining different genes. In this case, the genes are the unique features taken from the dataset randomly. Every chromosome in the population denotes one solution. The chromosome can be represented as a 1-D array with m cells.
- **Initial population:** The initialization process is the first step of GA, which involves creating an initial population of chromosomes randomly. This step specifies the population size (N) and the length of the chromosome (m), which is equal to the number of genes. For this work, initially, m is set to 10, which means each chromosome holds 10 random features. The gene at index i holds any feature value k . For instance, if a gene at index 1 holds value 6, it represents 6th feature from the original data.
- **Fitness function:** The fitness function assigns a fitness value to each chromosome, indicating its performance in the optimization problem. Here, we used the correlation as the fitness function. The Pearson correlation (R) between two features X and Y is calculated using Eq. (9). As a final solution, we need a feature set that have been diverse in nature and has a low co-relation. For which the average correlation value is presented in Eq. (10) must transfer to average non-correlation value using Eq. (11). The fitness function in Eq. (12) estimates maximization of the average un-correlation value.

$$R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (X_i - \bar{X})(Y_i - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (X_i - \bar{X})^2 \sum_{i=1}^N (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2}} \quad (9)$$

where X_i and Y_i are the features values for instance i , \bar{X} and \bar{Y} are their mean values.

$$Cor_{Avg} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{a,b=1}^N R_i, \text{ for } a < b \quad (10)$$

where R_i is the computed correlation matrix, and the sum of the above diagonal elements of the matrix is found. N is the total number of values.

$$Cor_{Avg}^T = 1 - Cor_{Avg} \quad (11)$$

where, Cor_{Avg}^T is the transferred average non-correlation value.

$$f_i = \max(Cor_{Avg}^T) \quad (12)$$

where, f_i returns the fitness value of i th chromosome.

- **Selection method:** The principle of survival of the fittest inspires the selection process. Chromosomes with higher fitness values are more likely to be selected for reproduction. The process involved in this work is based on tournament selection. We

Algorithm 1 Proposed GA-based Feature Selection Process

```

1: procedure GA FS
2: Input:  $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ , Population size,
3: crossover probability ( $cp$ ), mutation probability ( $mp$ )
4: Output: Top  $k$  features
5:   for specified number of generations do ▷ GA based FS
6:     for each chromosome in population do
7:       Evaluate fitness function of the chromosome using Eq. (12). ▷ tournament selection.
8:       Select chromosomes for crossover
9:       Apply crossover with  $cp$  ▷ one point cross over
10:      Apply mutation with  $mp$  ▷ add small value
11:      Replace the population with new chromosomes
12:     end for
13:   end for
14:    $feature\_new \leftarrow$  Best fit chromosome
15:   Apply MI on  $feature\_new$  and ranked the features.
16:   Return top  $k$  features.
17: end procedure

```

Table 3
Parameters settings of the GA model.

Parameters	Value
Number of generations	100
Chromosome population Size	60
no of features	10, 15, 20, 25
n_population	60
Crossover_probability	0.6
Crossover_independent_probability	0.5
Crossover Type	one point
Cross-validation	5
Mutation_probability	0.05
mutation_independent_probability	0.04
tournament_size	3

consider tournament selection as it introduces an element of randomness and diversity in parent selection, which can help prevent premature convergence.

The process randomly selects k individuals from the population to participate in a tournament. Further, it evaluates the fitness of each individual. The individual with the highest fitness in the tournament is considered the winner. The tournament winner is selected as a parent for the next generation.

- **Crossover operator:** The crossover operation involves exchanging genetic material between pairs of parent chromosomes to create offspring chromosomes. Crossover is performed by exchanging genetic material at crossover points. The crossover operation can be represented as the parent chromosomes P1 and P2. It can be of either a one-point or two-point scheme. In one point crossover, a selected pair of strings is cut at some random position, and then the segments are swapped to form a new pair of strings. In this paper, with 0.6 probability, we perform a one-point crossover by randomly choosing a crossover point.
- **Mutation:** The mutation operation introduces random changes in the genetic material of chromosomes to explore new solutions. Mutation helps to maintain diversity within the population and avoid premature convergence to sub-optimal solutions. We randomly choose a gene position for mutation operation and replace the gene with a randomly generated value. With a 0.05 mutation probability, we conducted our experiment.
- **Stopping criteria:** Stopping criteria specify when an algorithm, optimization process, or iteration should end. Here, the number of generations is considered the stopping criterion, after which the algorithm terminates.

The GA-based FS is illustrated in Algorithm 1. The algorithm begins with random population initialization, using numeric representations for genes. Individuals are evaluated by a fitness function, followed by selection, crossover, and mutation operators with specified probabilities. The process continues for a maximum of 100 generations, ultimately reducing the dimension of the dataset's features. Further, it employs MI to rank the features. The parameters used in GA are given in Table 3.

4.2. Proposed hybrid DNN model

After the implementation of GA, essential features were extracted, and training data (Tr) were fed to the designed hybrid DNN model for attack detection tasks. First, the input layer is set as $Input \in D^{batch \times 10 \times 1}$. The batch normalization (BN) is introduced to expedite the convergence of input data D with batch size 32. For each mini-batch of data passed through a neural network layer,

Fig. 3. Framework of the proposed hybrid DNN model.

BN normalizes the activations of that layer. Further, BN subtracts the mean μ and divides it by the standard deviation (σ) of the batch, which is expressed in Eq. (13).

$$L_i^{norm} = \frac{L_i - \mu}{\sigma + \epsilon} \tag{13}$$

where, L_i^{norm} is the normalization of layer (L_i) and ϵ is the smoothing factor. After normalizing, it introduces two learnable parameters, γ (scale) and β (shift). These parameters allow the network to learn the optimal scale and shift for the normalized activation, which is shown in Eq. (14).

$$L_i = \gamma L_i^{norm} + \beta \tag{14}$$

The DNN comprises multiple layers. It commences with a single convolutional layer followed by multiple RNN variants. The output of the batch normalization is fed into a convolutional layer employing 8 kernels, which is responsible for spatial feature extraction. In this layer, the convolution operation of a particular co-ordinate is carried out as follows:

$$Conv_{x,y} = \sum_{L_i} W_{L_i} T_{L_i} \tag{15}$$

where, W_{L_i} and T_{L_i} represents the weight and network traffic value respectively. A max-pooling layer is introduced n , which is used for a down-sampling operation that selects the maximum value within a local region. Next, the output of $Conv$ is $D^{batch \times 10 \times 8}$ and is fed into a ReLu nonlinear activation layer.

In order to capture the in-depth characteristics of input traffic, a combination of LSTM, Bi-LSTM, and Bi-GRU models is being utilized, each combining its own distinct advantages. While LSTM and GRU are effective in mitigating vanishing gradient issues, LSTM demonstrates superior classification performance. On the other hand, GRU has faster computational efficiency. Additionally, Bi-LSTMs and Bi-GRUs excel at capturing sequential dependencies, enhancing the overall data comprehension in both directions. The arrangement of these layers has been chosen experimentally to optimize performance. Individual dropout layers have been incorporated in both Bi-LSTM and Bi-GRU layers to prevent data overfitting. Lastly, a single dense layer, which combines the outputs of all preceding layers, is activated before analyzing the detection results. A graphical representation of the proposed hybrid network is presented in Fig. 3. The detailed network structure and optimal parameter settings of the proposed model are discussed in Table 5. Further details regarding the model are elaborated in the subsequent subsections. The discussed model performs well under the given

Table 4
Steps of the proposed H-DNN model.

Step 1: model.add(Conv(w_1, Tr))	$\triangleright w_1$ is the weight of convolutions layer
Step 2: model.add(LSTM(w_2, x_1))	$\triangleright w_2$ is the weight, x_1 is the input from the previous layer
Step 3: model.add(Bidirectional (LSTM(w_2, x_2)))	$\triangleright w_2$ is the weight and x_2 is the input
Step 4: model.add(Bidirectional (GRU(w_3, x_3)))	$\triangleright w_3$ is the weight of GRU layer
Step 5: model.add(Dropout-rate)	
Step 6: model.add(Bidirectional (GRU(w_4, x_4)))	$\triangleright w_4$ is the weight of Bi-GRU layer
Step 7: model.add(Dropout-rate)	\triangleright Adjusted hidden-layers weights using back-propagation
Step 8: model.add(Dense(w_4, x_3 , activation = Sigmoid))	

Table 5
Parameter settings of the end-to-end model.

Hyper-parameter	Activation function/values
1D-Convolution	tanh, neurons = 20
LSTM	Sigmoid, neurons = 64
Bi-LSTM	ReLU, neurons = 64
Bi-GRU	Sigmoid, neurons = 32
Bi-GRU	Sigmoid, neurons = 32
Dense	Sigmoid
Batch size	32
Learning rate	0.001
Optimizer	adam
Loss function	Binary-cross entropy
Dropout	0.5
Epochs	20
Total Feature (Both)	83,49
Reduced Feature (Both)	10,10

Table 6
Network structures.

Components	Output_Dim	Parameters
Input shape	[B, 10, 1]	B- Batch size = 32, Trainable Inputs
Batch Normalization	[B, 10, 1]	
Convolution	[B, 10, 3]	3, 1 × 3, ReLu
max pool	[B, 5, 3]	pooling size = 2
LSTM	[B, 10, 1]	[64 units, Activation]
Bi-LSTM	[B, 10, 1]	[64 units, Activation]
Bi-GRU	[B, 10, 1]	[32 units, Activation]
Bi-GRU	[B, 10, 1]	[32 units, Activation]
neuron	(10, 16 Batch size)	
activation	(0, 5)	Relu, sigmoid
flatten layer	Batch size 16	

training configuration: 10 selected features (both the dataset), a mini-batch size of 32, 20 epochs, with 0.001 training rate, and ReLU as the activation function. During training, an Adam optimizer is used, which adjusts the weights and corrects the biases of DNN's parameters. The steps involved in the training phase of the proposed H-DNN model are outlined in [Table 4](#).

The use of Bi-GRU is able to learn long-term dependencies in sequential data in both the forward and backward directions. This allows Bi-GRUs to capture more contextual information than traditional GRUs, which can only learn dependencies in the forward direction. It is constructed using two stacked GRU layers: one that processes the input sequence in the forward direction and one that processes the input sequence in the backward direction. The outputs of the two GRU layers are then concatenated to produce the final output of the Bi-GRU layer. The detailed network structure of the proposed model is discussed in [Table 6](#).

5. Experimental results and discussions

This section discusses the experimental setup and obtained results during the evaluation of the model. All experiments were conducted over a system which is having CPU Intel Core i7, 512 GHz, 1 TB RAM. Python 3.9 Anaconda and Jupyter Notebook IDE are other additional packages. Python's Tensorflow and Scikit-learn modules are utilized to develop DNN models.

Table 7

Selected features of UNSW-NB15, InSDN, and CICIoT datasets.

UNSW features	Description	Rank	InSDN features	Description	Rank	CIC-IoT features	Description	Rank
sttl	Source Time to Live	0.225	Timestamp	Date and of network flow	10.943	flow_duration	The duration of a network flow	4.471
dttl	Destination Time to Live	0.201	Dst IP	Destination Internet Protocol	9.387	rst_count	The count of TCP Reset (RST) packets observed	4.305
dwin	Destination window size	0.141	Flow ID	Network Flow Identifier	4.202	Header_Length	The length of the header portion of a network packet	2.376
swin	Source window size	0.142	FIN Flag Cnt	Count of finish flag in the network	3.373	Variance	Statistical measure that quantifies the degree of dispersion	1.394
dstip	Destination Internet Protocol address	0.137	Init Bwd Win Bytes	Initial backward window Bytes	3.213	ack_flag_number	The number of packets that have the acknowledgment (ACK) flag set in a network flow	1.181
srcip	Source Internet Protocol address	0.136	Src IP	Source Internet Protocol	1.742	Max	Metric within a network flow or communication session between IoT devices.	1.085
state	State of the Connection	0.128	SYN Flag Cnt	Count of Synchronize flags in the network flow	1.684	TCP	Transmission Control Protocol	0.842
ct-state-ttl	Connection State Time to Live	0.121	Dst Port	Destination Port	1.594	Radius	The radius of network traffic flows	0.767
sbytes	Source Bytes	0.115	Fwd IAT Mean	Forward Inter-arrival Time mean	1.253	Std	Standard deviation of a particular attribute	0.726
proto	Protocol	0.106	Bwd Pkts/s	Backward Packets per Second	1.186	rst_flag_number	The Reset (RST) flag set in a network flow	0.640

Table 8

Summary of datasets.

Specifications	InSDN	UNSW-NB-15	CICIoT-2023
Number of Features	84	49	47
Number of Classes	9	10	7
Number of samples	3,43,939	2.5 million	2.6 million
Attack samples	2,75,515	3,21,283	2,38,687
Normal samples	68,424	22,18,761	23,20,641

5.1. Dataset description

Three popular datasets, such as InSDN, UNSW-NB-15, and CICIoT, were taken into consideration to evaluate the performance of the proposed model. These datasets are well-known in the research community for containing a variety of network attacks. For our experiments, to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed model we used the entire datasets without segregating specific types of attacks, for detecting a broad range of cyber attacks.

InSDn dataset is the testbed generated dataset [48]. This dataset has been widely used for developing and evaluating IDS in SDN standards. Key characteristics such as *Flow ID*, *Src IP*, *Src Port*, *Dst IP*, and *Dst Port* allow identifying and monitoring data within SDN networks. Byte and packet based attributes hold the information related to the bytes and packets.

The UNSW-NB15 is a well-known network intrusion detection dataset developed by the University of New South Wales (UNSW) in Australia [49]. It was created specifically for evaluating and testing intrusion detection systems in network security research. This dataset comprises a comprehensive array of features essential for understanding traffic dynamics within the network. Attributes like *proto* and *state* delineate offer valuable context for analyzing traffic patterns.

The CICIoT-2023 [50] is a very recent and extensive dataset specifically designed for validating security analytics applications in real-time IoT operations. The data was collected from 105 real IoT devices, including smart sensors, smart home devices, lights, smart cameras, etc. Few selected IoT devices act as attackers and a few selected work as victims. Parameters like *Flow Duration*, *Flow IAT Mean*, and *Flow IAT Max* provide useful timing information for activity profiling. Additionally, statistical summaries like *totals*, *minima*, *maxima*, and *Std* provide deeper insights into traffic pattern analysis. Table 8 summarizes the data set description.

5.2. Data pre-processing and normalization

In this paper, we use pre-processing to handle null values. In the UNSW-NB-15 dataset, a few null values exist. This problem is handled by dropping rows and columns. Feature scaling is made using the standardization technique, which provides the values

Fig. 4. Convergence analysis of fitness function for GA .

to be centered on the mean with a unit standard deviation (SD). The mean value of the attribute becomes zero, and the resulting distribution has a unit standard deviation as follows.

$$x' = \frac{(x - \mu)}{\sigma} \quad (16)$$

where, μ is the mean of the feature values and σ is the standard deviation of the feature values. Standardization is helpful in cases where the data follows a Gaussian distribution as stated in Eq. (17).

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} e^{-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (17)$$

Moreover, the encoder technique has been used to label categorical data such as srcip, sport, service, dsport, state, proto, dstip, and attacks, etc..

Further, for both datasets, the data normalization process was performed to avoid high variance among the features. The min–max method was used for feature scaling, as discussed in Eq. (18).

$$x_n = \frac{x - x_{min}}{x_{max} - x_{min}} \quad (18)$$

where x_n denotes the normalized value ranging from [0,1] and x_{max} , x_{min} represents the maximum and minimum value of a particular feature in the dataset.

5.3. Performance metrics

The performance of the detection model is measured using different metrics such as accuracy, recall, F1-score, precision, and Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC). Accuracy measures how well these models perform on a specific task, with higher values indicating better performance. These are part of the confusion matrix, which is a function of True Positive (TP), True Negative (TN), False Positive (FP), and False Negative (FN). The MCC metric is used to measure the quality of classification models. It provides a balanced classification performance measure, considering TP, TN, FP, and FN.

5.4. Performance evaluation of GA-based FS

A set of experiments has been conducted by executing the GA-based FS on each of the benchmark datasets. This step enables the selection of a set of optimum features from the entire dataset to perform detection instead of utilizing all attributes of the data.

Analyzing both the average fitness and maximum fitness during the convergence analysis provides valuable insights into the algorithm's performance and behavior. If the average fitness increases and the maximum fitness improves, it suggests that the algorithm is exploring effectively. In Fig. 4, we study the fitness values of three different datasets. The average fitness and maximum fitness have been measured across multiple iterations. In InSDN dataset, the fitness values for both *avg_fitness* and *max_fitness* steadily improved as the genetic algorithm iterations progressed. The *avg_fitness* reached a high of approximately 0.921, while the *max_fitness* peaked at approximately 0.988. In UNSW-NB-15 dataset, the fitness values demonstrated consistent improvement over iterations. The *avg_fitness* reached a high of approximately 0.818, while the *max_fitness* peaked at approximately 0.896. In the final iterations, the InSDN dataset achieved significantly higher fitness values compared to the UNSW-NB-15 dataset. For CICIoT dataset, the *max_fitness* peaked at approximately 0.975. These results suggest that the GA performed effectively in optimizing the objective function for this particular dataset. The top 10 selected features from the three datasets, descriptions along with their ranks are presented in Table 7. Here, mutual information measures the degree of statistical dependency between each independent feature and the target feature. Separate experiments were conducted to select the best 10, 15, 20, and 25 features from the datasets.

Table 9

Performance matrix with the different feature set for attack detection of the proposed model (CNN+LSTM+Bi-LSTM+2(Bi-GRU)).

Performance Matrix	F-10	F-15	F-20	F-25
InSDN dataset				
Accuracy	98.66	97.41	97.90	96.25
Recall	98.74	84.09	87.19	97.73
Precision	99.67	85.11	84.52	85.39
F1-Score	99.19	82.34	85.72	87.01
Loss	0.0104	0.0293	0.0234	0.1389
UNSW NB-15 dataset				
Accuracy	99.14	99.25	99.17	99.28
Recall	99.44	93.87	92.89	95.05
Precision	99.17	99.17	99.15	100
F1-Score	99.30	95.75	100	97.87
Loss	0.0138	0.0312	0.0142	0.0371
CICIoT-2023 dataset				
Accuracy	99.78	98.54	99.23	99.19
Recall	98.76	99.38	98.91	96.75
Precision	100	98.40	97.59	100
F1-Score	98.45	97.32	98.80	98.37
Loss	0.0401	0.0459	0.0514	0.0757

Fig. 5. Comparison between training loss using proposed approach.

Fig. 6. Comparison between validation loss using proposed approach.

5.5. Performance evaluation of the hybrid DNN model

This experiment aims to evaluate the dataset using the combination of CNN with the Bi-LSTM and Bi-GRU model. After the feature selection process, the dataset with important features is directly fed to the proposed model. The detection is conducted in the testing phase. To measure the efficiency, we consider the basic LSTM model, Bi-LSTM, Attention-based LSTM, Bi-GRU, CNN, and CNN-LSTM model. Table 9 indicate that to achieve optimum accuracy, utilizing all available features is unnecessary. Employing only the top 10 features yields a commendable 97.64% accuracy, with a precision of 80.21% and a recall of 82.23% on the InSDN dataset, in contrast to using all 49 features, employing the best 20 features resulting in higher accuracy. On the other hand, for the UNSW dataset, the obtained accuracy, precision, and recall are as high as 99.25%, 99.01%, and 99.02%, respectively. Moreover, using only the 15 best features on this dataset leads to optimum accuracy. Recall is critical since it ensures that the model captures the majority of cyber attacks.

Remarkably, in all experiments, the lowest loss values are achieved with just 10 features. If attaining higher accuracy remains a priority, and only a marginal compromise is acceptable, an optimal trade-off that maximizes accuracy can still be attained. By

Fig. 7. Comparison between training accuracy using proposed approach (with and without FS).

Fig. 8. Comparison between validation accuracy using proposed approach (with and without FS).

Table 10

Comparison of attack detection among baseline models (InSDN Dataset).

Technique	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1-Score	MCC
LSTM [28]	98.91	99.28	94.01	96.57	99.46
Bi-LSTM [51]	98.92	93.28	94.01	94.28	90.64
Attention-LSTM	99.31	98.97	99.17	99.75	99.48
GRU [29]	97.45	98.3	95.23	96.74	94.53
CNN [52]	98.56	98.75	95.89	97.29	95.38
CNN-LSTM [45]	99.49	99.65	100	99.71	99.82
Proposed Model	98.66	98.74	99.67	99.19	99.03

utilizing only 10 features, the model sacrifices only a minimal fraction of accuracy, i.e. 0.56% on the InSDN dataset and 0.28% on the UNSW dataset, relative to their best achievable results.

Fig. 5 illustrates the loss evaluation of the models during the training phase for three datasets. The training loss is a measure of how well the DNN model is performing on the training data during each epoch. A decreasing training loss indicates that the network is learning and fitting the training data. The experiment shows that the proposed model regularly beats the model without FS in terms of loss reduction, which makes it a good option for detecting anomaly data where capturing context and dependencies is essential. On the other hand, Fig. 6 demonstrates the validation loss. It is a measure of how well the DNN generalizes to data it has not seen during training. We can see a comparatively better trend for the considered model during training loss. For three cases, shown in Figs. 6(a)–6(c) it is noticed that after utilizing FS, the model loss happens to start from a lower value compared to the original dataset. Also, it was found that the loss curve of the model was as stable as that of the original feature model. A smaller loss was realized for the InSDN dataset. In another experiment, a comparative analysis has been made on the accuracy w.r.t. epochs of the model as depicted in Fig. 7. The training accuracy curve for the proposed model steadily increased while no big gaps were noticed between the training and validation accuracies of the model with FS in either dataset. It indicated the model with FS does not fall under overfitting, as illustrated in Fig. 7. The model built from the InSDN dataset achieved the best accuracy shown in Fig. 8(a). In two other datasets, it achieved 98.67%, and 99.78% of validation accuracy, as shown in Figs. 8(b), 8(c) respectively. This emphasizes the importance of incorporating Bi-GRU and Bi-LSTM in the model which enhances performance.

Tables 10, 11, and 12 demonstrate a comparative analysis of the performance of various DL techniques considered for the detection scenarios in all the datasets. This analysis emphasizes the accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and MCC achieved by the model using the top ten features. It reveals that FS improves the accuracy, F1-score, and recall of all DNN models in all datasets. MCC values indicate the model's ability to classify binary outcomes correctly. The results suggest that the proposed hybrid model is slightly outperformed by the individual CNN-LSTM and LSTM models in terms of MCC. The GRU model, while decent, has the lowest MCC among the models.

The Area Under the Curve (AUC) serves as a quantitative metric for evaluating a model's discriminatory power, with higher values indicative of better overall performance. In the context of the InSDN dataset, the proposed model's higher AUC suggests

Table 11
Comparison of attack detection among base line models (UNSW Dataset).

Technique	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1-Score	MCC
LSTM [28]	98.16	98.05	98.02	98.43	99.46
Bi-LSTM [51]	98.18	98.91	98.43	100	97.93
Attention-LSTM	97.64	96.53	99.01	97.05	98.66
GRU [29]	99.83	94.41	98.55	100	99.65
CNN [52]	98.71	86.79	100	95.25	97.87
CNN-LSTM [45]	99.67	99.81	100	99.73	99.61
Proposed Model	99.14	99.44	99.17	99.30	98.27

Table 12
Comparison of attack detection among baseline models (CICIoT2023 Dataset).

Technique	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1-Score	MCC
LSTM [28]	98.32	98.55	99.11	98.73	97.12
Bi-LSTM [51]	99.52	98.62	99.25	99.05	98.09
Attention-LSTM	98.33	98.71	92.82	98.75	98.60
GRU [29]	99.63	100	95.91	93.65	98.21
CNN [52]	98.66	98.78	100	97.43	99.02
CNN-LSTM [45]	99.71	99.16	98.54	96.76	98.61
Proposed Model	99.78	98.76	100	98.45	99.25

Fig. 9. ROC-AUC analysis using three datasets.

its effectiveness in capturing underlying patterns, showcasing its ability to make accurate predictions and outperforming the other considered models. In Fig. 9, the selected features by the proposed model perform better than all features. This figure represents the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve for the models applied to both datasets. We can see a comparison of better performance in the considered model during testing time as shown in Figs. 9(a) and 9(b). Fig. 9(a), executed over the InSDN dataset and Fig. 9(c) executed on the CICIoT dataset. However, when compared to the model with all characteristics, the suggested model obtains a higher TPR across a range of FPR values, leading to a bigger area under the ROC curve (AUC) in the CICIoT dataset. Higher AUC values are indicative of better overall performance and serve as a quantitative tool for assessing a model's discriminatory capacity. In this instance, the AUC of the suggested model indicates how well it captures underlying patterns in the InSDN dataset, demonstrating its predictive accuracy. The respective confusion matrices that were obtained after FS are illustrated in Fig. 10. From the results, it is understood that the proposed model can detect attack traffic effectively.

Computational time provides an estimate of the duration we can anticipate for request processing. The computational time for the proposed model has been demonstrated in Fig. 12.

After dimensional reduction, a significant improvement can be observed in both the training and testing phases. Training the model with 10 features requires nearly 2,500 s, while the full feature demands nearly 4000 s in the InSDN dataset. On the other hand, after the feature reduction, the training time was also drastically reduced. Notably, increasing the number of features results in longer testing times. It is concluded that optimizing the training process can save resources, which is useful for IoT-like resource-constrained environments. Note that after dimensional reduction, the testing time is reduced by nearly 50% in all three datasets as depicted in Figs. 11(a)–11(c).

A comparative analysis of testing time and memory usage has been made in Fig. 12. Judging from Fig. 12(a), it can be noticed that the model's testing time is in an acceptable range. The model discussed in [28,40] uses high-dimensional CNN layers with a large number of kernels, which makes the model complex. The cascading layers without pooling operation used by [52], make the model computationally rich. On the other hand, the number of computations of the model is represented in Mega Floating-Point Operations (MFLOPs). MFLOPs is a metric that provides an insight into the computational complexity of DL models. It represents

Fig. 10. Confusion matrix for the proposed model.

Fig. 11. Computation time of the model.

Fig. 12. Comparative analysis of testing time (in sec) and MFLOPs.

the number of floating-point operations performed by the model, which are commonly used in neural network computations. Often, it estimates the computational requirements of a model and compares the efficiency of different architectures. According to the obtained results in Fig. 12(b), MFLOPs of the existing GRU model [8] contain the lowest operations. The findings indicate that the proposed model, with 20.14 MFLOPs, outperforms the CNN, Bi-LSTM, and LSTM models regarding time consumption. The model can be easily deployed over an SDIoT controller with lesser resource consumption. It is important to observe the performance of the proposed GA-based FS approach against the standard feature selection methods. Specifically, Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE), Sequential Feature Selector (SFS), and Backward Feature Elimination (BFE) were compared during this experiment. Each FS method was individually applied to CICIoT-2023 dataset, followed by selecting a subset of features for training using the proposed H-DNN model. Fig. 13(a) indicates that the SFS and RFE demonstrate better performance when feature sizes range from 5 to 9. However, as feature size increased, GA showed a gradual improvement in accuracy. In another experiment, we aimed to illustrate the balance between model accuracy and CPU utilization. The model achieves reasonable accuracy in most of the cases. Despite compromising accuracy, the lower CPU utilization makes the model more efficient. Specifically, the proposed GA+H-DNN model consumes CPU utilization at minimal levels, as depicted in Fig. 13(b), with values as low as 4.9%, 5.1%, and 6.3% across the three datasets.

Fig. 13. Comparison between different performance parameters.

6. Concluding remarks

The objective of this work is to streamline the input data to minimize the computational time and memory requirements without deteriorating the detection performance of an Intrusion Detection System (IDS) integrated with SDN controllers for IoT networks. In pursuit of this goal, the paper introduces a feature selection scheme based on genetic algorithms and combines it with a hybrid Deep Neural Network approach for attack detection within SDN-assisted IoT networks. The GA-based feature selection approach employs both correlation and mutual information as fitness functions and important feature ranking, respectively. The resulting reduced dataset is then fed into a hybrid DNN model, which incorporates various Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) variants, such as LSTM, GRU, and Bi-LSTM. These components are thoughtfully arranged to enable the model to analyze network traffic effectively using a limited feature set. Experimental evaluations were conducted using three distinct datasets: InSDN, UNSW-NB15, and CICIoT. The findings indicate that employing feature selection in the preprocessing stage significantly reduces model complexity and further lower CPU utilization makes the model efficient. A comparative analysis of the proposed model against RNN variants and a CNN model revealed its suitability for SDIoT scenarios. For future work, there is potential to enhance the DL approach further to reduce the execution time at the power crunch device. For example, reinforcement deep learning could be explored to address real-time labeled data challenges. Additionally, federated learning could be investigated as a use case, especially concerning edge devices within typical software-defined IoT networks.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Arati Behera: Visualization, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Kshira Sagar Sahoo:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Tapas Kumar Mishra:** Supervision, Software, Methodology. **Monowar Bhuyan:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Monowar Bhuyan and Kshira Sagar Sahoo report a relationship with Umeå University that includes: funding grants. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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